

How trust in stakeholders shapes social acceptance of Carbon Capture and Storage

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Abstract:

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) represents a key technological pathway for achieving net-zero goals, yet its success depends as much on public trust and social acceptance as on technical feasibility. This study investigates how trust in CCS stakeholders (scientists, institutions, and industry) influence social acceptance through perceived benefits and risks. Data were collected from 800 participants in Poland and the Czech Republic, two countries developing CCS as part of their industrial decarbonization strategies. Using Structural Equation Modeling, we tested a model in which trust predicts perceived benefits and risks, which in turn influence social acceptance, and conducted an exploratory moderation analysis to assess whether trust shapes the relationship between perceived risks and acceptance. Results show that trust strongly increased perceived benefits ($\beta = .58$) and was positively associated with perceived risks ($\beta = .15$), suggesting that trust can coexist with awareness of technological risks. Both perceived benefits and risks significantly mediated the relationship between trust and acceptance, and a direct effect of trust on acceptance ($\beta = .28$) remained significant. Perceived benefits emerged as the strongest predictor of acceptance ($\beta = .66$), while perceived risks had a weaker negative effect ($\beta = -.10$). The moderation analysis revealed that higher trust enhances sensitivity to risks without reducing support, consistent with the notion of reflexive trust. These findings suggest that trust does not eliminate risk perception but promotes informed and legitimate acceptance. Strengthening transparent communication and participatory governance may therefore enhance public confidence and support for CCS deployment across Europe.

Keywords:

Carbon Capture and Storage; social acceptance; perceived benefits; perceived risks; structural equation modeling

44 **1. Introduction**

45 Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is widely recognized as an important technology
46 for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from hard-to-decarbonize sectors such as cement
47 and steel production (Gür, 2022; McLaughlin et al., 2023). Yet, its successful
48 implementation depends not only on technological and economic feasibility but also on
49 its social acceptance (Karytsas et al., 2023; Nielsen et al., 2022; Witte, 2021).

50 In this context, social acceptance refers to the extent to which individuals and
51 communities support or tolerate CCS projects, reflecting a broader willingness to live
52 with or endorse them (Moon et al., 2020; Whitmarsh et al., 2019). It is shaped by
53 psychological and societal factors, such as perceptions of fairness, legitimacy, and trust
54 in stakeholders, which determine whether CCS is viewed as a credible or contested
55 climate solution (Glanz and Schönauer, 2021; Klaus et al., 2020; Milani et al., 2024).

56 At the psychological level, acceptance is influenced by individual evaluations of the
57 technology's outcomes. Perceived benefits (e.g., climate protection, local economic
58 opportunities, job creation), perceived risks (e.g., safety, leakage), and the degree of trust
59 in stakeholders jointly shape how people perceived the legitimacy of CCS initiatives (Cox
60 et al., 2020; Terwel et al., 2009).

61 Trust functions as a psychological shortcut that shapes how people process
62 information about CCS and interpret uncertainty. As stakeholders act as the main
63 interface between the technology and the public, trust influences how messages are
64 received: high trust emphasizes perceived benefits and moderates risks, whereas low trust
65 amplifies danger and unfairness perceptions (Nielsen et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2023).

66 Departing from this general trend, some studies indicate that trust in stakeholders, and
67 its relationship with acceptance, can take a more reflective form, when individuals
68 maintain confidence in those responsible for the technology while remaining aware of
69 potential risks associated with its implementation. This so-called reflexive trust reflects a
70 confidence that persists despite awareness of uncertainty and potential technology
71 fallibility (Craye et al., 2005; Myskja, 2024).

72 Beyond psychological mechanisms, the acceptance of CCS technologies depends on
73 contextual and structural factors. Local economic conditions, regulatory stability, and
74 broader environmental priorities shape perceptions of legitimacy and fairness, influencing
75 whether communities engage with or oppose CCS initiatives (Myskja, 2024, Satterfield
76 et al., 2023; Zuch and Ladenburg, 2023). These dynamics define the environment in
77 which individuals form their attitudes, affecting how trust and risk/benefits perceptions
78 translate into support, ambivalence, or opposition. For instance, projects linked to local
79 employment are often seen as more legitimate, whereas those limited community
80 relevance or unclear benefits tend to elicit skepticism and resistance (Nielsen et al., 2022).

81 Although previous research has highlighted the roles of trust in stakeholders,
82 perceived benefits, and perceived risks in explaining social acceptance, these factors have
83 often been examined separately, or without distinguishing between different targets of
84 trust. Most studies treat trust as a general belief in institutional competence or fairness,
85 overlooking how trust in specific actors, such as governmental authorities, scientists, or
86 industry, may differently shape evaluations of CCS (Terwel et al., 2009; Wesche et al.,
87 2023). Yet evidence suggests that people's willingness to support CCS depends on

88 whether they trust the stakeholders who communicate, regulate, and benefit from it
89 (Cologna and Siegrist, 2020; Fikru and Nguyen, 2024).

90 The present study addresses this gap by examining how trust in CCS stakeholders
91 influences perceived benefits and perceived risks. Integrating these components within a
92 single structural model provides a comprehensive view of how institutional and
93 psychological dimensions jointly shape acceptance. The study focuses on Poland and the
94 Czech Republic, where CCS initiatives are emerging as part of industrial decarbonization
95 strategies. These cases offer an opportunity to examine how trust-based evaluations
96 operate in regions with limited public familiarity with CCS.

97 In essence, the study tests a structural model linking trust, perceived benefits,
98 perceived risks, and social acceptance to offer an integrated perspective on the
99 psychosocial mechanisms shaping acceptance of low-carbon technologies.

100 101 **2. Theoretical framework**

102 ***2.1 Trust in CCS stakeholders and perceived benefits***

103 According to the literature, when people have limited direct knowledge or
104 experience with CCS, trust acts as a psychological mechanism to manage uncertainty
105 about the technology's reliability and the intentions of those promoting it. In such
106 cases, stakeholders like scientists, institutions, and project developers become reference
107 points whose perceived competence and integrity shape expectations of potential benefits.

108 Terwel et al. (2009) distinguished between competence-based and integrity-based
109 trust, showing that higher competence-based trust enhances perceptions of CCS benefits,
110 while low integrity-based trust increases sensitivity to stakeholders' motives. Building on
111 this, Cologna et al. (2022) and Gao et al. (2022) demonstrated that under low familiarity
112 or high uncertainty, trust functions as an affective heuristic, fostering optimistic
113 evaluations of CCS outcomes such as environmental protection and economic growth.

114 More recent studies (Mahjour and Faroughi, 2023; Xie et al., 2023) extend this view,
115 showing that trust strengthens perceived benefits by reducing ambiguity about
116 technological performance (uncertainty reduction), amplifying positive affective
117 associations with responsible actors (affect heuristic), and reinforcing expectations that
118 CCS will deliver tangible advantages for society (expectancy of positive outcomes).

119 Trust also conveys normative legitimacy, the belief that the technology serves a
120 collective good and is managed by transparent, competent institutions (Tardin-Coelho et
121 al., 2025). Evidence from European and Chinese studies shows that higher trust in
122 scientists, NGOs, and governmental authorities predicts stronger perceptions of social
123 and environmental benefits, whereas low trust in industry or opaque actors weakens them
124 (Moon et al., 2020; Witte, 2021).

125 These findings suggest that stakeholder trust enhances perceived benefits by shaping
126 both affective and cognitive appraisals of CCS. Trusted actors make benefits appear more
127 salient and credible, embedding the technology within a broader narrative of fair and
128 legitimate energy transition.

132 **2.2 Trust in CCS stakeholders and perceived risks**

133 In emerging technologies such as CCS, risk perception not only depends on technical
134 knowledge but also by the level of trust placed in those managing and communicating
135 about risks. While trust typically reduces uncertainty and fear by assuring individuals that
136 the technology is competently and safely handled (Karimi, 2021; Terwel et al., 2009),
137 recent literature suggests that the relationship is not always strictly inverse. When
138 stakeholders communicate risk openly and transparently, or when trust is grounded
139 primarily in perceived competence rather than integrity, trust may coexist with risk
140 awareness, encouraging more reflective engagement with risk information.

141 In such cases, trust functions not merely as reassurance but as a factor that fosters
142 critical attention to risk communication, a more reflexive form of trust that accommodates
143 awareness of risks without diminishing confidence in the technology. This dynamic, often
144 described as the trust–risk paradox, shows how trust and critical scrutiny can coexist
145 (Määttä and de Gooyert, 2025; Siegrist, 2021).

146 Evidence from CCS research supports this dual role. Tsvetkov et al. (2019) found that
147 trust in industry, NGOs, and governmental stakeholders shapes both benefit and risk
148 perceptions: transparent communication about safety and responsibilities reduces public
149 concern, whereas limited or conflicting information increases uncertainty and protest
150 potential. Similarly, Stavrianakis et al. (2024) showed that trust can coexist with critical
151 awareness, as communities remain confident in institutions while recognizing residual
152 risks that must be managed transparently.

153 Trust may also shape how people process risk information more directly. When trust
154 is high, individuals evaluate risk information through the lens of institutional credibility,
155 which can alter its perceived importance for acceptance (Siegrist, 2021). Overall, the
156 literature indicates that trust in CCS stakeholders functions as a psychological and
157 relational mechanism shaping how individuals interpret technological risks. High trust
158 typically reduces perceived risks, yet can also foster reflexive trust, allowing awareness
159 of uncertainties while maintaining confidence in the technology’s legitimacy and fairness
160 (Myskja, 2024).

162 **2.3 Perceived benefits, perceived risks, and social acceptance**

163 Perceived benefits and perceived risks are key cognitive appraisals through which
164 individuals evaluate emerging technologies such as CCS (Huijts et al., 2012; L’Orange
165 Seigo et al., 2014). These judgments reflect expectations of desirable outcomes or
166 potential uncertainties. Both dimensions shape public attitudes and are consistently linked
167 to social acceptance (Zuch and Ladenburg, 2023).

168 Empirical findings show that perceived benefits are positively related to CCS support,
169 whereas perceived risks are negatively related (Xu et al., 2023). Yet these effects are not
170 symmetrical: benefits generally exert a stronger influence, suggesting that positive
171 expectations outweigh moderate safety concerns. Fürst and Strunge (2024) found that
172 when individuals believe CCS contributes to emission reduction, innovation, or regional
173 development, such beliefs foster acceptance, whereas reassurance about safety alone
174 rarely increases willingness to support it.

175 This asymmetry was also noted by the Zero Emissions Platform (2024), a European
176 advisory body on CCS and Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU). The report shows that
177 transparent communication of collective benefits enhances perceived legitimacy, whereas
178 communication focused solely on minimizing risks often leads to ambivalent reactions,
179 indicating that advantages carry greater motivational weight.

180 Together, these findings suggest that increases in perceived benefits strengthen
181 acceptance, whereas higher perceived risks weaken it. This imbalance indicates that
182 public evaluations of CCS are guided less by affective caution than by deliberative
183 assessments of its usefulness and fairness.

184 185 ***2.4 The mediating role of perceived benefits and risks***

186 Trust shapes CCS acceptance mainly through how individuals evaluate its potential
187 outcomes (Terwel et al., 2009). Rather than influencing support directly, trust in
188 stakeholders affects how people weigh expected benefits and possible risks. When
189 institutions and experts are seen as competent, transparent, and accountable, individuals
190 are more likely to judge CCS as beneficial and its risks as manageable. These appraisals
191 translate institutional credibility into evaluations of usefulness, fairness, and safety
192 (Große-Kreul et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2016).

193 Empirical research confirms that perceived benefits and risks act as key mechanisms
194 linking trust to acceptance. Studies consistently show that higher trust is associated with
195 stronger expectations of climate and social benefits and with lower concern about safety
196 or long-term impacts (Kahlor et al., 2020; Karytsas et al., 2023; Moon et al., 2020; Zuch
197 and Ladenburg, 2023). Perceived benefits generally emerge as the stronger predictor of
198 acceptance, while perceived risks exert a weaker but negative effect (Milani et al., 2024).
199 These findings suggest that trust fosters acceptance not by merely reducing fear, but by
200 shaping how citizens interpret and balance CCS outcomes.

201 This mediating process highlights trust as a cognitive and relational foundation for
202 acceptance. Trust in competent stakeholders encourages people to view CCS within a
203 broader narrative of responsible climate action, while low trust amplifies uncertainty and
204 limits engagement. Understanding this indirect pathway clarifies how trust contributes to
205 public support, less as a guarantee of safety and more as a condition enabling balanced
206 evaluation of benefits and risks.

207 208 ***2.5 Trust in CCS stakeholders and social acceptance***

209 Trust can also influence CCS acceptance more directly. When institutions and experts
210 are perceived as competent, transparent, and acting in the public interest, people may
211 support CCS as a legitimate form of climate action even amid uncertainty. This link
212 reflects a normative dimension of trust, where acceptance rests on perceptions of moral
213 credibility and institutional integrity rather than solely on evaluations of risks and benefits
214 (Terwel et al., 2011; Witte, 2021).

215 Yang et al. (2016) and Xie et al. (2023) showed that trust in CCS stakeholders
216 significantly predicts public support even when risk and benefit perceptions are
217 considered. Terwel et al. (2009, 2011) further demonstrated that competence- and
218 integrity-based trust can directly foster acceptance, especially when organizations are

219 seen as serving collective interests and acting transparently rather than pursuing self-
220 interest. In contrast, Wallquist et al. (2012) found that trust loses explanatory power when
221 opposition is driven by strong ideological beliefs, suggesting that its direct impact
222 depends on both context and the dimension of acceptance examined.

223 Trust also functions as social approval. When governance is viewed as fair and
224 participatory, and communication as open and consistent, trust in stakeholders provides
225 the moral basis for acceptance (Tcvetkov et al., 2019; Witte, 2021), expressing confidence
226 that CCS will be managed responsibly and in alignment with collective values, sustaining
227 support even under uncertainty.

228

229 **2.6 Current study**

230 The present study aims to evaluate the mediating role of perceived benefits and
231 perceived risks in the relationship between trust in CCS stakeholders and social
232 acceptance of CCS. We examine trust in stakeholders as a key psychological factor
233 shaping how individuals evaluate this emerging technology. The analysis used data
234 collected in Poland and the Czech Republic, two countries involved in a CCS project
235 assessing its feasibility and social acceptance within climate-mitigation strategies.
236 National differences are included to account for contextual variation.

237 We propose and test a structural model in which trust in CCS stakeholders predicts
238 both perceived benefits and risks of CCS, which in turn influence social acceptance (see
239 Figure 1). A direct path between trust and acceptance assesses whether trust fosters
240 acceptance beyond cognitive evaluations of risks and benefits.

241 Additionally, a moderation analysis examines whether trust moderates the negative
242 relationship between perceived risks and social acceptance, offering a complementary
243 view of how trust interacts with risk awareness. All these hypotheses are summarized
244 below:

245 **Hypothesis 1 (H1).** Higher trust in CCS stakeholders will be positively associated with
246 perceived benefits of CCS.

247 **Hypothesis 2 (H2).** Higher trust in CCS stakeholders will be negatively associated with
248 perceived risks of CCS.

249 **Hypothesis 3 (H3).** Perceived benefits will be positively associated with social
250 acceptance of CCS.

251 **Hypothesis 4 (H4).** Perceived risks will be negatively associated with social acceptance
252 of CCS.

253 **Hypothesis (H5).** Trust in CCS stakeholders will directly and positively predict the social
254 acceptance of CCS, independently of the mediating roles of perceived benefits and
255 perceived risks.

256 **Hypothesis (H6).** Perceived benefits will mediate the relationship between trust and
257 social acceptance of CCS.

258 **Hypothesis (H7).** Perceived risks will mediate the relationship between trust and social
259 acceptance of CCS.

260 **Hypothesis (H8).** Trust in CCS stakeholders will moderate the negative relationship
261 between perceived risks and social acceptance, such that the association will be weaker
262 among individuals with higher trust.

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267

[INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE]

268 **3. Materials and methods**

269 **3.1 Participants and procedure**

270 The final sample consisted of 800 participants, equally distributed between Poland (n
271 = 400) and the Czech Republic (n = 400). This size meets recommended criteria for
272 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), providing sufficient power (>.95) to detect medium
273 effects in models of moderate complexity (Kline, 2016; MacCallum et al., 1996).

274 Participants were 18 years or older. 53.8% were female and 46.3% were male. The
275 age distribution was balanced: 11% aged 18–24, 19% aged 25–34, 24% aged 35–44, 20%
276 aged 45–54, 15% aged 55–64, and 11% were 65 years or older.

277 Regarding employment, 55.5% were employed full-time, 9.3% part-time, and 5.5%
278 self-employed, while smaller proportions were unemployed (4.5%), students (4.8%), or
279 homemakers/caregivers (4.9%). Additionally, 13.8% were retired and 1.9% unable to
280 work. About one third, 32.3% lived near a large industrial facility, whereas 67.8% did
281 not. Perceived household income was heterogeneous: 38% described it as average, 34%
282 below average, and 26% above the national average.

283 Education levels reflected national systems. In the Czech Republic, 5% had only
284 primary education, 24% lower secondary, 45% secondary with final exam, 24%
285 university, and 2% doctoral. In Poland, 0.3% had only primary, 3.5% lower secondary,
286 37% higher secondary, 12% vocational, 33% university, and 14% postgraduate or
287 doctoral.

288 Data were collected via online survey in September 2025 by a professional company
289 ensuring national representativeness by gender, age, and region. Participants, recruited
290 from national panels, received a small incentive. Before starting, they were informed
291 about the study’s purpose, data protection, and withdrawal rights, and gave informed
292 consent. The survey took approximately 10–15 minutes.

293 The questionnaire was developed in English and translated into Polish and Czech
294 using translation and back-translation to ensure conceptual and linguistic equivalence.
295 Pilot tests confirmed clarity and contextual appropriateness. Data collection complied
296 with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the university’s ethical standards.

297

298 **3.2 Measures**

- 299 • *Trust in CCS stakeholders* was measured using eight items adapted from Große-
300 Kreul et al. (2021). Participants indicated how much they trusted 8 institutional
301 and social actors involved in or related to CCS, including national and local
302 authorities, energy companies, the European Union, research institutions,
303 environmental NGOs, and the media. Responses were recorded on a 6-point scale
304 (1 = not at all; 5 = very high; 6 = don’t know). Cronbach’s alpha = .88
- 305 • *Perceived benefits of CCS* were measured using five items from Xu et al. (2023).
306 Participants rated their agreement with statements regarding the positive effects

307 of CCS, including its contribution to climate change mitigation, air quality
308 improvement, economic development, regional image, and job creation Sample
309 items include “CCS could mitigate climate change”. Responses were recorded on
310 a 6-point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree; 6 = don’t
311 know). Cronbach’s alpha = .88.

312 • *Perceived risks of CCS* were measured using eight items based on Slovic’s (1987).
313 Items covered multiple risks dimensions, including perceived frequency and
314 severity of accidents, uncertainty about long-term consequences, and feelings of
315 dread and uncontrollability. Sample items include “Accidents in CO₂ storage sites
316 are likely to occur”. Responses were given on a 5-point Likert scale from 1
317 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Cronbach’s alpha = .84.

318 • *Social acceptance of CCS* was measured using five items adapted from Arning et
319 al. (2019). Participants rated statements evaluating the usefulness, value, and
320 acceptability of CCS, as well as their overall support for its implementation.
321 Sample items include “I think CCS is useful”. Responses were recorded on a 7-
322 point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree; 6 = strongly agree; 7 = don’t know).
323 Cronbach’s alpha = .84.

324 Reliability was satisfactory in both national samples. In the Czech Republic,
325 Cronbach’s alpha ranged from .81 to .86 across constructs (Trust = .86; Benefits = .85;
326 Risks = .81; Acceptance = .86). In Poland, ranged from .82 to .91 (Trust = .89; Benefits
327 = .91; Risks = .86; Acceptance = .82), indicating good internal consistency and cross-
328 national comparability. Responses marked as ‘don’t know’ were excluded in descriptive
329 analyses and were treated as missing data in the SEM models. Composite scores for each
330 construct were computed by averaging item responses.

331

332 **3.3 Data analyses**

333 Analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 30 and IBM SPSS AMOS 27.
334 Preliminary analyses included descriptive statistics, bivariate correlations, and reliability
335 coefficients (Cronbach’s α).

336 To test H1–H7, a series of Structural Equation Models (SEM) examined relationships
337 among trust in CCS stakeholders, perceived benefits of CCS, perceived risks of CCS, and
338 social acceptance of CCS. The analysis was designed to assess both the direct associations
339 hypothesized in H1–H5 and the indirect effects proposed in H6–H7.

340 Trust was modeled as an exogenous variable, perceived benefits and perceived risks
341 as mediators, and social acceptance as the outcome (endogenous constructs). Country was
342 included as a control variable predicting all endogenous constructs, following
343 recommendations for contextual control (Byrne, 2016; Kline, 2016).

344 Three competing SEMs were specified. Model 1 (M1) assumed full mediation, with
345 trust predicting social acceptance only indirectly through perceived benefits and
346 perceived risks. Model 2 (M2) tested partial mediation by adding a direct path from trust
347 to social acceptance. Model 3 (M3) kept this structure but added correlated residuals
348 among indicators within the same latent construct, as suggested by modification indices,
349 to account for shared variance not captured by the structural paths.

350 All models were estimated using maximum likelihood. Model fit was evaluated with
351 χ^2 , df, CFI, TLI, and RMSEA (90% CI). Following Schreiber (2017), CFI and TLI \geq .90
352 and RMSEA \leq .08 were considered acceptable. Indirect effects were tested following
353 MacKinnon's (2002) approach, using bias-corrected bootstrapped confidence intervals
354 (5,000 resamples).

355 Missing data ranged from 5% to 8% for trust and benefits (due to the 'don't know'
356 option) and were treated as missing in the SEM. No missing data were observed in the
357 risk scale. Social acceptance items showed higher missingness (15%), likely reflecting
358 limited familiarity with CCS. All 'don't know' responses were imputed using Multiple
359 Imputation (MI) to reduce bias (Rubin, 1996).

360 In addition, an exploratory moderation analysis (PROCESS Model 1; Hayes, 2012)
361 tested H8, examining whether trust moderates the relationship between perceived risks
362 and social acceptance. Variables were mean-centered, and 5,000 bootstrap samples were
363 used to estimate confidence intervals for the interaction term.

364 **4. Results**

365 **4.1 Descriptive analyses**

366 Table 1 shows the means, standard deviations, and intercorrelations among the study
367 variables (N = 800), trust in CCS stakeholders, perceived benefits, perceived risks, and
368 social acceptance. All variables showed acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha \geq$.84). As
369 expected, trust correlated positively with perceived benefits ($r = .41$, $p < .01$) and social
370 acceptance ($r = .40$, $p < .01$), while its correlation with perceived risks was small and non-
371 significant ($r = .05$, n.s.). Perceived benefits were strongly and positively associated with
372 social acceptance ($r = .57$, $p < .01$) and weakly with perceived risks ($r = .13$, $p < .05$). The
373 correlation between perceived risks and social acceptance was negative but non-
374 significant ($r = -.04$, n.s.).

375 [INSERT TABLE 1 HERE]

377 **4.2 Structural Equation Modelling analyses**

378 In SEM tests for H1 and H2, results supported both hypotheses, with trust showing a
379 strong positive effect on perceived benefits ($\beta = .62$, $p < .001$) and a smaller but significant
380 positive effect on perceived risks ($\beta = .15$, $p < .001$). The fully mediated model (M1),
381 showed acceptable fit, $\chi^2 = 1400.01$, $df = 295$, $p < .001$, RMSEA = .068 (90% CI [.065,
382 .072]), TLI = .869, and CFI = .890.

383 For H3-H5, M2 added a direct path from trust to social acceptance. This partial
384 mediation model showed slightly improved fit, $\chi^2 = 1321.44$, $df = 294$, $p < .001$, RMSEA
385 = .066 (90% CI [.063, .070]), TLI = .878, CFI = .898. All paths were significant ($p <$
386 $.001$): trust positively predicted perceived benefits ($\beta = .74$) and perceived risks ($\beta = .15$),
387 and directly predicted social acceptance ($\beta = .53$). Perceived benefits positively predicted
388 acceptance ($\beta = .89$), while perceived risks had a negative effect ($\beta = -.21$). The inclusion
389 of the direct path confirmed H5 while retaining the indirect effects through benefits and
390 risks.

391 For H6–H7, M3 tested the partially mediated structure with correlated residuals
392 suggested by modification indices. Three residual covariances were added within
393 constructs: TrustCCS7–TrustCCS8 ($r = .35, p < .001$), Risks1–Risks2 ($r = .38, p < .001$),
394 and SA4–SA5 ($r = .50, p < .001$), justified by semantic similarity.

395 M3 provided the best fit, $\chi^2 = 979.07, df = 291, p < .001, RMSEA = .054$ (90% CI
396 [.051, .058]), TLI = .928, CFI = .936. All direct and indirect paths were significant ($p <$
397 $.001$). Trust predicted perceived benefits ($\beta = .58$) and risks ($\beta = .15$). Both trust ($\beta = .28$)
398 and benefits ($\beta = .66$) positively predicted acceptance, while risks showed a weak
399 negative effect ($\beta = -.10$). Country (control variable) had small but significant effects on
400 trust ($\beta = .28, p < .001$), benefits ($\beta = .16, p = .001$), risks ($\beta = .18, p < .001$), and
401 acceptance ($\beta = .14, p = .003$), indicating slightly higher values in Poland but consistent
402 structural relationships across contexts. Trust explained 32% of variance in benefits and
403 7% in risks; together, trust, benefits, and risks accounted for 44% of variance in
404 acceptance.

405 Indirect effects estimated through bias-corrected bootstrapping (5,000 resamples)
406 confirmed mediation. The indirect effect of trust on acceptance through benefits was
407 positive and significant ($\beta = .32, 95\% \text{ CI } [.27, .38], p < .001$), supporting H6. The effect
408 through risks was small and negative ($\beta = -.02, 95\% \text{ CI } [-.04, -.01], p < .01$), supporting
409 H7.

410 As in the previous models, the positive association between trust and perceived risks
411 remained significant, confirming the pattern observed in M1 and M2. This finding
412 suggests that higher trust may reflect greater engagement and awareness of potential risks
413 without implying their rejection, consistent with earlier studies on CCS and other low-
414 carbon technologies, a dynamic often described as the trust–risk paradox.

415 Fit indices for all SEM models are summarized in Table 2, and the final model (M3)
416 is shown in Figure 2, retained as the most parsimonious and theoretically consistent
417 representation of relationships among trust, perceived benefits, perceived risks, and social
418 acceptance.

419 [INSERT TABLE 2 HERE]

420 [INSERT FIGURE 2 HERE]

424 **4.3 Exploratory moderation analyses**

425 To further explore the interplay between trust and risk perception, a moderation
426 analysis was conducted using PROCESS Model 1 (Hayes, 2012) tested H8, proposing
427 that trust in CCS stakeholders moderates the relationship between perceived risks and
428 social acceptance. The interaction between perceived risks and trust was marginally
429 significant ($\beta = -.09, p = .053$), indicating a weak moderation trend. As shown in Figure
430 3, the negative association between perceived risks and acceptance was non-significant
431 at low trust ($\beta = -.08, p = .15$) but became significant and progressively stronger at
432 medium ($\beta = -.16, p = .001$) and high trust ($\beta = -.21, p = .001$).

433 [INSERT FIGURE 3 HERE]

435 **5. Discussion**

436 The present study investigated how trust in CCS stakeholders influences social
437 acceptance of CCS through both direct and indirect pathways involving perceived
438 benefits and risks. The SEM results supported most of the hypothesis, clarifying the
439 cognitive mechanisms underlying social acceptance. Hypotheses 1, 3-7 were confirmed,
440 while H2 was not. Trust strongly predicted perceived benefits (supporting H1) and
441 showed a small but significant positive association with perceived risks (not supporting
442 H2). Perceived benefits were the strongest positive predictor of social acceptance (H3),
443 while perceived risks negatively predicted it (H4). The direct from trust to acceptance
444 remained significant (H5). And both variables mediated the relationship between trust
445 and social acceptance (H6-H7). Together, these variables explained a substantial
446 proportion of the variance in social acceptance, highlighting the centrality of cognitive
447 appraisals in public support for CCS.

448 Including country as a control variable confirmed that the overall pattern was
449 consistent across both national samples, reinforcing the model's robustness. Nevertheless,
450 participants from Poland reported slightly higher trust, perceived benefits, and social
451 acceptance than those from Czech Republic, but structural paths remained stable across
452 contexts.

453 These results align with broader European trends. Studies from Northern and Western
454 Europe (like Germany, the Netherlands, Norway, and the UK) report moderate levels of
455 trust and risk perception, alongside more favorable evaluations of benefits and acceptance
456 (ENSURE Report, 2024; Mascarenhas et al., 2025; Witte, 2021). Results for Poland and
457 the Czech Republic fall within this broader European pattern, with slightly higher
458 perceived benefits and acceptance. This suggests a form of cautious optimism, in which
459 people combine moderate trust with awareness of technological risks but still view CCS
460 positively as a climate-mitigation option. The slightly higher acceptance may also be
461 linked to growing policy attention to industrial decarbonization and to the relatively
462 limited direct experience with CCS projects in these countries.

463 The study also showed that the direct effect of trust in stakeholders on social
464 acceptance remained significant even after including benefits and risks as mediators,
465 indicating that trust contributes to acceptance not only indirectly through its influence on
466 how people perceive the benefits and risks of CCS, but also directly, reflecting general
467 trust in institutions and actors promoting CCS. This pattern aligns with previous research
468 showing that trust reflects both trust in competence and perceptions of integrity (Terwel
469 et al. 2009, 2011), suggesting that trusted actors are expected to manage the technology
470 transparently and effectively.

471 A particularly notable finding concerns the relationship between trust and perceived
472 risks. Contrary to the usual expectation that higher trust reduces risks perception
473 (Tcvetkov et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2016;), this study found a small but significant positive
474 association. Participants with higher trust also recognized slightly more risks, consistent
475 with research suggesting that trust does not necessarily diminish risk awareness (Myskja,
476 2024). Those who trust relevant stakeholders may be more attentive to information about
477 both benefits and risks, reflecting a more engaged and informed stance toward the
478 technology.

479 The moderation analysis (H8) further clarified this dynamic. The negative link
480 between perceived risks and acceptance was stronger among individuals with higher trust,
481 indicating that trust did not buffer risk effects. Even those who trusted stakeholders most
482 were sensitive to potential risks, reflecting a form of reflexive trust (Myskja, 2024), in
483 which confidence coexists with critical awareness and acceptance depends on the belief
484 that competent institutions manage risks transparently. Although modest, this effect
485 supports H8 and shows that trust shapes how individuals interpret and respond to risks
486 rather than neutralizing them.

487 In summary, three key insights emerge. First, trust influences acceptance both directly
488 and indirectly. Second, perceived benefits have a stronger influence than risks, suggesting
489 that positive expectations outweigh safety concerns. Third, the coexistence of trust and
490 risk awareness challenges the notion of trust as mere reassurance, indicating instead that
491 it promotes informed and reflective engagement with CCS. These findings have important
492 implications for understanding technology acceptance and for designing communication
493 strategies that strengthen public trust in CCS.

494

495 ***5.1 Theoretical and practical implications***

496 This study advances theoretical understanding of the social acceptance of CCS by
497 integrating trust in CCS stakeholders, perceived benefits and risks of CCS within a single
498 explanatory model. Previous research had identified these variables as separate predictors
499 of acceptance (Huijts et al., 2012; L'Orange Seigo et al., 2014), but their combined effects
500 had rarely been tested. The present findings show that trust in stakeholders has both
501 cognitive and normative components, shaping how people evaluate expected outcomes
502 and how they judge the legitimacy of responsible institutions

503 The results also refine assumptions about how trust relates to perceived risks. While
504 traditional models suggest that trust simply reduces risk perception, the positive
505 association observed here reveals a more complex dynamic. In this case, trust coexisted
506 with risk awareness, consistent with the notion of reflexive trust: confidence grounded in
507 competence and transparency yet accompanied by critical awareness and expectations of
508 accountability (Nielsen et al., 2022; Siegrist, 2021). Individuals who trust capable and
509 transparent institutions do not ignore risks but remain attentive to uncertainties while
510 continuing to support the technology.

511 A further contribution concerns the influence of benefits and risks. Consistent with
512 recent research, perceived benefits emerged as stronger predictors of acceptance than
513 perceived risks (Arning et al., 2021; Fikru and Nguyen, 2024; Shah et al., 2022; Xu et al.,
514 2023). This pattern indicates that positive expectations about technological outcomes,
515 such as emission reduction, climate mitigation, or job creation, carry greater motivational
516 weight than the absence of concern. Benefit perception may activate approach-oriented
517 evaluations, whereas risk perception tends to generate avoidance responses that are less
518 decisive when the technology is regarded as useful and socially beneficial.

519 The persistence of a direct path from trust to social acceptance, even after accounting
520 for benefits and risks, underscores the normative role of trust as an indicator of
521 institutional legitimacy. This finding echoes previous evidence that acceptance depends
522 not only on cognitive appraisals but also on whether institutions are perceived as

523 transparent, fair, and morally credible (Cox et al., 2020; Whitmarsh et al., 2019). As such,
524 integrating this normative layer clarifies how trust continues to shape support beyond
525 perceptions of risk and benefit.

526 From a practical perspective, fostering trust involves more than reassuring messages
527 about safety. Communication benefits from acknowledging uncertainties, addressing
528 potential risks transparently, and explaining how they are monitored and managed. Open
529 discussion of risks does not necessarily reduce acceptance; rather, it can strengthen
530 reflexive trust, where confidence coexists with critical awareness. The effectiveness of
531 such communication depends on shared psychological, cultural, and social dynamics that
532 appear consistent across contexts. Although small cross-national differences emerged, the
533 stability of the model across both countries indicates that strategies to foster trust and
534 communicate CCS risks and benefits may rely on similar mechanisms. Thus,
535 communication approaches developed in one context are transferable, with cultural
536 sensitivity, to other European settings.

537 At the same time, the finding that perceived benefits are stronger predictors of
538 acceptance than risks highlights the importance of communicating CCS advantages
539 concretely while avoiding one-sided or overly optimistic framings. Linking CCS to
540 observable environmental and social outcomes (e.g., emission reduction, climate goals,
541 job creation) is most persuasive when accompanied by clear explanations of safety
542 measures and institutional accountability. Risk and benefit communication is most
543 effective when integrated into a transparent narrative that recognizes both opportunities
544 and limitations.

545 Finally, because trust reflects broader judgments of legitimacy, governance processes
546 ensuring fairness, participation, and responsiveness are essential for maintaining social
547 acceptance over time. Engaging local actors in planning, monitoring, and benefit-sharing
548 can transform communication into ongoing dialogue that sustains public confidence and
549 long-term legitimacy.

550

551 ***5.2 Limitations and future research***

552 Although this study provides valuable insights into how trust in stakeholders,
553 perceived benefits, and perceived risks shape social acceptance of CCS, several
554 limitations should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design prevents drawing
555 causal conclusions about the directionality of the relationships. The associations observed
556 between trust, cognitive appraisals, and acceptance should be interpreted as correlational.
557 However, the large and balanced sample across two national contexts strengthens the
558 generalizability of the findings and provides a robust basis for future longitudinal
559 investigations.

560 Second, the study relied on self-reported measures, which may be influenced by social
561 desirability and respondents' subjective interpretations of CCS. Although validated scales
562 were used and reliability indices were high, future research could combine survey data
563 with qualitative approach to capture more nuanced perceptions and behaviors.

564 Third, although data were collected in two countries, it was not possible to conduct a
565 full multi-group or measurement invariance analysis because the relationship between
566 trust and perceived risks was non-significant in one country, which prevented establishing

567 a comparable structural pattern across groups. Instead, country was included as a control
568 variable to account for contextual differences. While this approach allowed testing the
569 overall robustness of the structural relationships, future studies could explicitly assess
570 measurement equivalence to confirm the cross-national comparability of constructs.

571 Future research should build on these results by adopting longitudinal or cross-lagged
572 designs to examine how trust, risk perception, and acceptance evolve as CCS projects
573 move from planning to implementation. Comparative studies across countries with
574 different levels of CCS maturity could illuminate contextual differences in trust formation
575 and risk communication. Incorporating variables such as perceived knowledge, media
576 exposure, and local engagement would also provide a deeper understanding of the
577 psychological and social processes underlying CCS acceptance.

578

579 **6. Conclusions**

580 This study examined how trust in CCS stakeholders influences social acceptance
581 through perceived benefits and risks, using structural equation modeling on samples from
582 Poland and the Czech Republic. Trust increased perceived benefits and showed a positive
583 association with perceived risks; both variables mediated the link between trust and
584 acceptance, and a direct path from trust to acceptance remained significant.

585 Beyond confirming established relationships, the results reveal that high trust can
586 coexist with risk awareness and that this combination is support greater acceptance. This
587 perspective interprets it as a reflective attitude, which enables individuals to evaluate
588 technologies critically while maintaining confidence in the actors responsible for their
589 development. In this sense, trust does not eliminate perceptions of risks but helps people
590 to interpret and contextualize them, recognizing uncertainty as an inherent feature of
591 innovation.

592 Within the context of climate and environmental challenges, such trust may facilitate
593 acceptance of CCS by fostering a belief that risks can be responsibly managed through
594 competent, transparent, and accountable institutions. In fact, this pattern aligns with
595 research on other low-carbon technologies. Studies on hydrogen energy and offshore
596 wind show that institutional trust can sustain public support even when safety concerns
597 or procedural uncertainties persist, provided that governance is transparent and fair in
598 their communication (Firestone et al., 2020; Jikiun et al., 2023). These parallels suggest
599 that informed, reflexive forms of trust may represent a broader mechanism shaping public
600 responses to emerging climate technologies, including CCS.

601 To conclude, this study contributes to promoting the responsible and socially
602 sustainable deployment of CCS across Europe. By demonstrating that informed trust can
603 foster acceptance, it emphasizes the importance of transparent communication,
604 participatory governance, and credible institutional engagement as foundations for
605 socially legitimate climate innovation.

606

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830 **Table 1.** Descriptive statistics and correlations among all study variables.

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4
1. Trust in CCS stakeholders	3.12	1.05	—			
2. Perceived benefits of CCS	3.79	0.94	.41**	—		
3. Perceived risks of CCS	3.48	0.60	.05	.13**	—	
4. Social acceptance of CCS	4.39	1.28	.40**	.57**	-.04	—

831 **Note.** M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation. N = 800. ** p < 0.01, * p < 0.05.

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865 **Table 2.** Goodness of fit indexes for tested SEM Models.

Model	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	p	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	Lower	Upper
M1 Full Mediation	1400.01	295	4.75	< .001	.869	.890	.068	.065	.072
M2 Partial Mediation	1321.44	294	4.50	< .001	.878	.898	.066	.063	.070
M3 Partial Mediation + MI	979.07	291	3.36	< .001	.928	.936	.054	.051	.058

866 **Note.** χ^2 = Chi-square; df = degrees of freedom; χ^2/df = relative Chi-square; p = probability; TLI =
867 Tucker–Lewis Index; CFI = Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of
868 Approximation; Lower and Upper = 90% confidence interval for RMSEA; MI = Multiple Imputation.

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Figure 1. Proposed model illustrating hypothesized relationships among trust in CCS stakeholders, perceived benefits, perceived risks, and social acceptance. H6 and H7 indicate mediated effects through perceived benefits and risks (shaded areas). Country was included as a control variable for all endogenous constructs. **Note.** CCS = Carbon Capture and Storage.

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Figure 2. Final model of the partial mediation model with modification indices. Standardized path coefficients are shown. Country was included as a control variable predicting all endogenous constructs. $p < .05 = *$, $p < .01 = **$, $p < .001 = ***$. **Note.** CCS = Carbon Capture and Storage; SA = Social Acceptance.

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Figure 3. Moderation effect of trust on the relationship between perceived risks and social acceptance of CCS